

Automation and telemechanics systems and devices in ensuring the safety of train traffic on metropolitan lines

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Annotation: The article proposes automation and telemechanic systems and devices in ensuring the safety of traffic on metropolitan lines. In today's world, the safety is the upmost feature in making selection about the transportation. Based on this, distinctive analysis and tables are proposed and solutions are provided.

Key words: operation, railway sections, scientific work, metropolitan, passage, safety.

Introduction

The bandwidth of a Metropolitan line is said to be the maximum number of trains (number of cars) of a fixed length that can pass within a unit of time (within 1 hour). The ability to conduct is divided into different groups: necessary, existing and project.

The type of conduction method by which the movement of trains, taking into account the Reserve time, must ensure the passage of cars of a specified volume, is called the necessary conductivity; existing conduction capacity - this is carried out without carrying out any capital construction work on the line and making changes in its designs, project conduction capacity-this can be achieved by carrying out the necessary modernization work or construction measures: by modernizing the autoblock systems, by increasing the power of the power supply system, by introducing new train control systems, etc.

The ability to carry passengers on the Metropolitan line is said to be the number

of passengers transported in one direction per unit of time (1 hour).

Passenger capacity on the A-Metropolitan line;

N-The number of carriage pairs on the metro line in 1 hour

n-number of cars;

V-Cars have a capacity of.;

$$A = N \cdot n \cdot v \quad (1)$$

1. The ability to ensure the safety and permeability of train traffic on metropolitan lines existing in the world

Increasing the permeability of trains at stations can be achieved by switching to controlling through a dynamic block-section system at metro stations. We can see this possibility in companies such as Bombardier, Siemens, Thales, which are being used in their practice in foreign metro plots. It is possible to convey 90 Seconds of intervals between trains (40 pairs) by applying the systems of companies SVTS (train control based on communication channels).

In order to ensure the safety of movement, trains in the subway can be achieved by providing a minimum safe distance by transmitting their parameters to the train onboard computer running behind the subway train.

In this case, the limiting factor in the stations and the capacity of the accelerators is considered. Calculations show that:

- the speed of access to the station does not exceed 55 km / h;
- the station is allowed to enter only after the action content leaves its entirety;
- parking time 25 C;
- platform length 200 m
- the duration of the interval between trains is at least 60 seconds, that is, - up to 60 pairs of trains per hour will be equal.

There are five groups of motion automation of Metro Trains (automation classes, GoA:

- GoA0-visual control of trains will be similar to control of street tram traffic;
- GoA1-partially automated mode, suitable for fully manual train movement control;
- GoA2-corresponds to the mode of semi-automatic control of the movement of trains. This mode is an analogue of the Avtovedeniya mode;
- GoA3-automatic mode, but the control of the movement of trains in non-standard situations of machinst (Stewart) takes over;
- GoA4-fully automatic mode is performed without human factor in train control.

2.1 Suggestions for ways to increase permeability.

There are several types and methods of increasing the throughput of stations and

bringing it to the throughput of trains, which are as follows:

- Reduce the length of the protective plot behind the plot where the exit traffic light is located. This makes it possible to reduce the vaccine by 12 s;
- By installing an additional traffic light before the main traffic light (signal). This serves to reduce the train entry time to the station by 5-7 s;
- Speed control of trains departing from the station;
- Can be reduced by 1.5 s time by taking the hitchhiking signals to a distance of 20 m to the opposite side of the train movement;
- Control the speed of trains entering the station;
- By limiting the maximum speed of approaching trains to the station;
- By controlling the train through a strict and rhythmic mode;
- Reduce the start time of signaling centralization blocking devices. It currently has 3 s. This time should be lowered to 0.5-1 s;
- There are 2 ways to increase the bandwidth of the traffic light closest to the station platform:

1) reducing the length of the station plot to 20 m, approaching the traffic light and the hitchhiking signal (near the end of the platform), which reduces the interval to about 1.5 s;

2) by installing an additional traffic light on the station platform, it will be possible to reduce this interval by another 3 seconds;

- Train rational speed selection;
- Transfer of existing relay electrical centralization systems to microprocessor systems at metropolitan stations.

N	Name	T time	N currently	N proposed	I v	A currently	A proposal
1	1 hour	1	20	60	7 00	28000	84000
2	1 day	18	360	1080	7 00	9072000	27216000
3	365 days	657 0	1314 00	39420 0	7 00	1,209E+ 12	3,626E+ 12

Table 1. Passenger capacity on the Metropolitan line

An electric centralization system has been launched in the Tashkent metro.

Tashkent Metro is a 5 km long Tashkent Metro line with 43 stations.

According to the data (4th edition), today 67% of the speeds of the electrical marking of relays available at the metro stations of V. I. Lenin. This led to the fact that out of 43 existing metro stations, microprocessor marking systems were implemented at 29, and microprocessor marking systems were implemented at 14

stations.

Figure 1. The state of electrical centering systems being fed at metropolitan stations

2.2 Problems arising in relay electrical centralization systems can be overcome by implementing new microprocessor-based electrical centralization systems at metropolitan stations.

The principle of operation of the existing dispatch centralization system in the Tashkent Metro

Metropolitan stations are linked to dialog dispatch centralization systems, which has the following Figure 5 appearance.

The dialogue dispatch centralization system is part of the group of microprocessor dispatch centralization systems. However it is not currently interconnected with the electrical centralization systems of the newly built metropolitan stations. This is due to the fact that manufacturers of microprocessor electrical centralization systems currently under design are not disclosed dialogue dispatch centralization system manufacturers software binding codes of the system. Therefore, the 14 new types of microprocessor systems listed above were proposed by 3 manufacturers, each of which installed its own dispatch center in the Tashkent Metropolitan dispatch centralization post.

Figure 2. Connection of electric centralization systems at metro stations with systems of interactive dispatch centralization

3 The principle of operation of the proposed microprocessor electrical centralization system of the Tashkent Metro

MPM microprocessor centralization is a new generation of control system implemented at the software level based on its algorithm designed to centralize its Arrows and signals at railway and metropolitan stations.

The MPM is designed to centrally manage signalling centralisation lock facilities at stations and adjacent peregons in order to ensure the safety of train traffic and increase train throughput.

Advantages of MPM over relay electrical centering system include:

- High level of reliability by repeating many nodes, including the MPM kernel, and continuous information sharing between this processor and control and control objects (which also helps to increase the level of security);
- ability to control the objects of many stations and peregons from one

workplace;

- the ability to integrate control of SMB devices and Motion Content state control devices in a single station processor;

- an extended set of technological functions, including plots reserved for closing the route without opening the traffic light, blocking arrows in the desired position, prohibiting traffic light, excluding route adjustment, etc;

- the ability to provide operational and technical personnel with detailed information about the status of SMB devices at the station, transfer this and other information to the regional transport control center;

- the possibility of placing object managers centrally and decentralized in the control station and working objects. The decentralized location of the object controller can significantly reduce the consumption of a special cable for one centralized arrow;

- relatively simple installation with high-end control systems;

- ability to manage objects at stations and to continuously record the actions of operational personnel in the entire state of the train;

- the presence of built-in diagnostic monitoring of the state of centralization devices and control objects;

- the possibility of registering the numbers of trains passing through stations and trains, as well as all failures of control facilities;

- significantly smaller dimensions of the equipment and, as a result, 3-4 times the size of the premises for its placement, which makes it possible to replace outdated centering systems without building new posts;

- significant reduction in construction and installation work;

- convenient connection verification technology without installing a layout using special tools;

- reducing the period of decommissioning of the station and its devices in cases where the connections between the track, arrows and signals have changed;

- the use of not only copper conductor cables, but also fiber optic cables as a means of transmitting information between control devices and controlled objects;

- obtaining the performance parameters of SMB field devices from the archive, then predicting their condition or planning repairs and adjustments, preventing the complete incapacity of these devices;

- reduce operation costs by reducing the energy consumption of the system, reducing the number of electromagnetic relays and the length of internal cables, using modern power supplies, eliminating large volume control panels and a large number of manipulators;

- reduction of handles and buttons that have a mechanical effect from processing.

Figure 3. Microprocessor centralization systems used at metro stations
Conclusion

A complex of automated dispatch control system to ensure the safety of train's work at stations on the Metropolitan line of computing devices the software functions of auto modes should perform the following tasks:

- device diagnostics and system self-diagnostics;
- automatic disconnection connection of zone circuit by one or two trains;
- software testing of devices before starting the action;
- disconnecting the planned supply and voltage of the contact in the metropolitan;
- disconnect from the contact rail from the emergency voltage.
- automated system for the formation of a standard train schedule.
- automated system for drawing up a schedule of movement of completed trains.
- automated system of economic transport planning.
- automatic control system for moving content.
- system of registration and transmission of operational data from onboard devices.
- automated system of processing devices that register information on board.
- Automated system of accounting and analysis of automated control system

lines.

If metropolitan areas are designed as an automatic dispatch centralization complex there will be an opportunity to reduce the intervals between trains while ensuring traffic safety.

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